

GREEN ERA-HUB
on Agri-Food and Biotechnology

Is anyone *really* monitoring impact?

Insights on impact assessment: Learnings from the Green ERA-Hub networks' experience

Research highlights

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WHY THIS RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS MATTER

A qualitative and quantitative mixed-methods coding analysis of official reports from 15 research networks in the Green ERA-Hub (GEH) and supported by interviews to project and network managers, suggest that current monitoring tools for international research cooperation in the HE programme are better suited to demonstrating accountability and transparency than to tracking actual impact. In practice, impact assessment often relies on strong assumptions about knowledge transfer rather than evidence of – or contribution to – change or who benefited from research outputs. This gap becomes more evident since the European Commission’s shift from a logic-model approach to a Theory of Change, operationalised through the Pathways to Impact framework (Bruno & Kadunc, 2019). The change of logic-model calls for a corresponding shift in evaluation practice. Moreover, the Pathways to Impact framework require tailored indicators, longer time horizons, and follow-up mechanisms that extend beyond the formal end of research programmes.

While developing adjusted key performance indicators (KPIs) for Scientific and Economic Impact is relatively straightforward, Policy and Societal Impact remain poorly defined, weakly traced, and inadequately assessed. Yet these pathways are central to demonstrating progress towards European policy goals and the uptake of scientific and technological developments by society, highlighting the importance of science-policy interfaces.

INTRODUCTION

This document capitalizes on the accumulated GEH experience to learn from initiatives and projects that have successfully created impact in transnational research collaborations. This document aims to share from the different networks’ experiences and deliver recommendations to improve practices for future research collaborations, including to the Horizon Europe Partnerships.

To this end, this research highlights document pays particular attention to impact and dissemination reports from 15 networks and JPIs part of GEH. These reports provided a long-term perspective on definitions of impacts achieved, dissemination of their knowledge, and evaluations and assessments of initiatives. Additionally, the report includes the outcomes of semi-structured interviews with network managers and PI researchers financed through ERA-Net calls. These semi-structured interviews focused on identifying positive factors for the success of their projects/initiatives, needs experienced, main contributions, views on the impacts of their work, and steps necessary to amplify their impact in either policy or practice. These interviews were primarily collected during the back-to-back shared workshop between FACCE-JPI and GEH, organized from 8 to 9 October 2024 in Berlin. Lastly, this study presents a list of recommendations including redefining evaluation and assessment criteria to foster impact in more targeted ways. The document suggests a framework to assess and

LESSONS FROM THE NETWORKS

Impact takes time. The most impactful networks reportedly ran for more than four years and combined realistic objectives and low personnel turnover, especially of key network managers . Networks of people matter as much as networks of institutions. Stable relationships with ministries, farmers, and other stakeholders improve benefits’ uptake. Mandatory call requirements on co-production, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and other stakeholder engagements facilitate impact, particularly when they are supported by guidance and funding.

IMPLICATIONS FOR HORIZON EUROPE AND FURTHER FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES

Assessment should be rebuilt around a Theory of Change (Mayne, 2017; Quinn, 1988; Rogers, 2008), explicitly developing adequate KPIs, defining impact as beneficiaries of research outcomes.

Societal impact - identified in the study as the second-largest reported impact area after scientific impact- needs a dedicated framework built around scales of impact informing impact-tailored KPIs.

Policy impact should not be treated as just another societal impact category; it requires separate indicators focused on uptake, awareness, critical mass development, and strong science policy networks, among others.

Traceability of impact must continue after the end of programmes, since there is currently no formal mechanism to follow impact once a network ends. Networks are not capable

identify realistic levels of societal impact. Although these recommendations are not exhaustive, they are an initial step towards considering impact from science to policy and practice in a systematic and systemic way across international research cooperation efforts

of providing long-medium and long term traceability. However, HE Partnerships could plan follow up assessments.

CORE FINDINGS

Current reporting often makes assumptions of impact based on metrics of accountability, like website visits or number of participants in a workshop, rather than evidencing a particular effect or establishing targeted knowledge transfer activities.

Multiple definitions of impact are being used in different work packages, which makes comparison difficult and encourages compliance-oriented reporting instead of focused impact goals.

Policy impact is different and must be traced differently than other societal impact; each needs a framework to develop logic and adequate metrics.

WHAT INTERVIEW EVIDENCE ADDS

Stakeholder engagement can redirect research toward more usable outputs. One researcher described a policy brief as their most impactful publication because it reached investors, industry, media, and policymakers.

However, incentives are misaligned: outputs with clear real-world reach and impact may still count little in tenure tracks.

Noteworthy, project outputs with promising results often stall after funding ends because no other actor carries further research towards proof-of-concept or other TRL.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR RESEARCH PROGRAMME MANAGERS

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| 1. Define impact clearly | Use a single operational definition anchored in beneficiaries of outcomes (Reed, 2018) , then specify separate pathways for scientific, societal, economic, and policy impacts. |
| 2. Assess change, not just output | Replace or complement accountability indicators with evidence of contributions to behavioural, institutional, regulatory, or practice changes attributable to a network's work. |
| 3. Separate policy from societal impact | Develop dedicated policy impact indicators - for example citation in strategies, direct use by ministries, generating science-policy networks, or requests for follow-on advice, contributions establishing a discourse in policy process, etc. |

4. Support post-project knowledge transfer

Create intermediary mechanisms or databases that connect researchers, public authorities, and market actors able to advance technologies and practices to higher readiness levels.

5. Secure long-term traceability

Plan - through REA, partnerships, or member states - for following outcomes after programme end so delayed impacts are not lost.

6. Implement top-down stakeholder engagements

Design calls with mandatory stakeholder engagement practices like RRI, co-creation, living labs or citizen science elements to promote a larger impact from individual projects.

BOTTOM LINE

GEH's experience suggests that impact assessment should move from counting deliverables to tracing how research networks influence decisions, institutions, policy, practices, economic and scientific activity, technology development, public opinion and science-policy-society interfaces over time.

PROPOSED FRAMEWORK FOR SOCIETAL IMPACT

Societal impact in the HE's Pathways to Impact is loosely defined and difficult to assess. Pathways like "Delivering impacts and benefits via R&I missions" or "Addressing EU policy priorities & global challenges through R&I" are difficult to conceptualize, assess and report in a consistent systematic manner, that allows for comparison across other societal impacts pathway implementations.

In order to ground the Societal Impact assessment, this study proposes a Framework for Societal Impact inspired by Reed (2018); and Reed et al. (2018) work on research impact. The purpose of the Framework is to list intended Policy and/or Societal Impacts and then implement a series of scales that help ground a realistic goal. This realistic goal informs the development of adequate KPIs for societal or policy impacts' assessments.

Below is the proposed framework for societal impact

Societal Impact Framework													
Type of intended societal impact	Stakeholders Scale	Geographical scale				Time scale		System scale *			Adoption scale **	KPIs Pathways to impact	
	<i>Stakeholders (in)directly benefited</i>	<i>Local</i>	<i>Regional</i>	<i>National</i>	<i>International</i>	<i><5 years</i>	<i>>5 years</i>	<i>Micro</i>	<i>Meso</i>	<i>Macro</i>		<i><5 years</i>	<i>>5 years</i>
<i>Impact to policy</i>													
Awareness and understanding of research in policy networks Attitudes and critical mass creation in publics Networking in science-policy-society interactions Knowledge Inputs for Public Policy Other impacts													
<i>Impact to society</i>													
Early adotions in production practices Changes in relation to the environment Human living conditions & wellbeing Decision making in organizations Normative changes in society Knowledge transfer Other impacts													

* Micro = applied in production / applied research. Meso = scientific or academic / institutional knowledge / ERA network /research network. Macro = public policy / sector / research system / food system

** **Conceptual:** impact is only framed in theory or strategy. **Planned:** pathways, KPIs, or structures exist, but no convincing realised effects yet. **Early signal:** first indications of use or change, but evidence is still limited, local, or provisional (e.g. received policy briefs).

Adopted: there is clear evidence of use beyond the project team, for example by stakeholders, policy makers, networks, or organisations. **Commercialisation:** there is evidence of products, services, or tools reaching the user or market oriented development (TRL 4-9).

Institutionalised: impact is embedded in stable governance,public policy, coordination structures, recurring programmes, or policy-facing institutions.

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